

Preparation of superhydrophobic copper film with excellent corrosion resistance by electrochemical deposition

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Abstract - Superhydrophobic copper film with excellent corrosion resistance were successfully prepared by forming the micro/nanostructure and modifying hydrophobic capric acid by one-step electrochemical deposition. The prepared superhydrophobic copper film exhibited excellent self-cleaning capability and corrosion resistance with a water contact angle of 151.5°. Compared with the original copper plate, the corrosion current of the fabricated superhydrophobic copper surface is about 1/50 of the original copper plate.

Keywords - Superhydrophobic film, Copper, Corrosion resistance, Electrochemical deposition.

I. INTRODUCTION

Wettability is an important property of solid surface, which is usually measured by the contact angle (CA) and the sliding angle (SA) of the surface. Solid surface is defined as superhydrophobic surface, while the contact angle is higher than 150° and sliding angle is lower than 10° [1,20]. In general, micro-nano-scale roughness and modification of low surface energy materials are two keys to the fabrication of superhydrophobic surfaces [3,4]. In recent years, several methods have been developed to fabricate superhydrophobic surfaces, such as sol-gel method [14,16,21,23], electrochemical deposition method [5,6], etching method [7], self-assembly method [2], chemical vapor deposition method [15], plasma treatment [8,11], and hydrothermal synthesis [24], etc. For example, most methods for preparing superhydrophobic surfaces require precise reaction conditions, complicated processes, and expensive or environmentally harmful reagents. Therefore, to explore a simple process, low-cost, environmental friendly superhydrophobic surface with good mechanical properties and physical and chemical stability is a research focus.

Due to its excellent water repellency, superhydrophobic surfaces are widely used in various fields, such as self-cleaning [9], resistance reduction [17], anti-icing [18], anti-fouling, anti-corrosion [19], and water-oil separation, etc. As we all know, corrosion is a common problem for most metals. It has important practical way to protect metals from being corroded effectively. Due to the non-wetting nature of the superhydrophobic surface, it may be a good solution for metal corrosion by coating a superhydrophobic film on the metal surface. A researcher used $Ce(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ to etch the magnesium plate and then modified fluorosilanes with low surface energy to obtain a corrosion-resistant magnesium-based superhydrophobic surface [12]. Compared with the untreated magnesium surface, the corrosion current of the superhydrophobic magnesium surface decreases. Since the surface tension of oil is much less than that of water, the superhydrophobic surface is oleophilic. Therefore, the water-oil mixture can be effectively separated by the difference of wettability between water and oil.

Copper is a widely used metal due to its mechanical properties, high strength, stable physical and chemical properties, acid-base resistance and high temperature (low temperature) resistance. Today, copper is widely used because of its excellent properties. Copper is an important metal material

used in industry and in our daily life. Superhydrophobicity can be imparted to copper plates to have special properties such as frost protection, corrosion protection, and minimizing resistance to flow in microfluidic devices [10,21]. Thus, superhydrophobic copper has greater potential applications in some harsh environments. Several methods have been developed to fabricate many artificial superhydrophobic copper surfaces. For example, A researcher developed an easy method to fabricate a hierarchical structure of copper oxide on copper substrates by oxidation of copper in hot alkaline solutions [22]. Many methods, such as electrochemical deposition [5,6] and sol-gel [21], have been used in recent years to form superhydrophobic surfaces on copper surfaces. However, most of the techniques described above require special equipment, several steps, a specific substrate or a harsh chemical treatment. Therefore, it is necessary to fabricate superhydrophobic copper surfaces in a simple and inexpensive way.

In this study, we prepared superhydrophobic copper surfaces with excellent corrosion resistance by chemical modification of capric acid, which is a micro/nano superhydrophobic structure and hydrophobic, on copper surfaces by simple, mild conditions, low cost and good reproducibility. The voltage and time of the electrochemical deposition process under ambient conditions are 20 V and 3 h, respectively. The prepared superhydrophobic copper surface has excellent self-cleaning and corrosion resistance. Due to its simplicity, excellent water repellency, good mechanical durability and chemical stability, the prepared superhydrophobic copper surface has good application prospect in fabricating samples of any appropriate size.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials

Anhydrous ethanol, 10% NaOH, 10% HCl, acetone, capric acid ($\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_8\text{COOH}$), simultaneous sample (99.993%), and abrasive paper (500 grades). All chemicals were pure and deionized water was used in all experiments and tests.

Preparation of superhydrophobic copper film

First, two copper plates (10mm×50mm×2mm) were ground with abrasive paper, dipped in 10% NaOH solution for 20 min, taken out and washed several times with deionized water. The copper plates were then immersed in 10% hydrochloric acid for 30 min, removed and washed several times with deionized water. Finally, the solution was sonicated in ethanol for 30 min and dried at 80 °C.

Then, the capric acid was dissolved in absolute ethanol at a constant concentration and two copper plates of 10 mm × 50 mm × 2 mm were immersed. The distance between the two copper plates was set to 2 cm and different voltages (5 V to 30 V and 5 V intervals) between the two electrodes were applied at different times (1 to 4 h and 1 h intervals) at room temperature. The prepared samples were washed with ethanol and deionized water and then dried at 80 °C.

Sample characterization

Water contact angle (WCAs) was measured by a contact angle meter (JC 2000C1, China) at room temperature. The contact angle is the average of five measurements obtained at different positions on sample's surface with droplets of 6 μL . The surface functional groups were measured by Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FT-IR, Tensor 27, Bruker Optics, Germany).

The structure and composition of the samples were analyzed by X-ray Powder Diffraction (XRD, D8 Advance, Bruker, Germany) with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418 \text{ nm}$) at a scanning rate of 0.02 s/step. The surface morphologies of the samples were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEM-2100P, JEOL, Japan). The corrosion resistance evaluation of the samples was measured in 3.5% NaCl solution for potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopic (EIS) by electrochemical analyzer (AutoLab, Metrohm). The electrochemical impedance spectra (EIS) were recorded in a frequency range of 0.01–105 Hz at open circuit voltages.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical composition of the sample surface

The chemical composition of the sample surface was analyzed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and X-ray powder diffraction.

Fig. 1 shows the results of Fourier transform infrared spectra of the prepared sample surface and capric acid. As shown in Fig. 1, the FTIR curves of the prepared sample surface and capric acid are similar to each other. The sample surface exhibited absorption peaks at 2954 cm^{-1} and 2835 cm^{-1} , which were attributed to C-H asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations, respectively. In addition, the absorption peak at 1710 cm^{-1} was observed in capric acid, which corresponds to carboxyl (-COO). On the other hand, the surface of the prepared samples showed absorption peaks at 1585 cm^{-1} and 1411 cm^{-1} , which could be attributed to the

asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of the -COO group. This indicates that the capric acid group was modified on the prepared sample surface.

Fig.1 FTIR curves of prepared sample films and capric acid Then, the XRD curve of sample surface is shown in Fig. 2. As shown in Fig. 2, the peaks at 2θ values of 42.5°, 50.1°, and 74.2° are attributed to the (111), (200) and (220) crystal planes of Cu, respectively. From the above results, it can be seen that the sample surface consists of Cu crystals.

Fig. 2 XRD patterns of sample film.

Surface morphology of the sample

Fig. 3 shows the process of producing superhydrophobic surfaces on copper substrates. The copper substrate was first ground and then electrochemical deposition was carried out in

ethanol solution of capric acid.

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of preparing superhydrophobic film on copper substrate.

The reason for copper caprate formation in copper substrate can be interpreted as follows. Copper is easily oxidized in air or under humid conditions. This is because copper is oxidized by oxygen in the air. When capric acid ($\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_8\text{COOH}$) is dissolved in ethanol, copper is slowly oxidized by oxygen in solution. Adding a positive voltage to the copper increases the rate of oxidation. Therefore, Cu^{2+} is released from the anodic copper plate as ethanol solution of $\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_8\text{COOH}$. Thus, the oxidation of copper takes place at the anode.

Anode: Cu - 2e → Cu²⁺ (oxidation)

When copper is released from the anode to Cu²⁺, the solution will contain Cu²⁺, capric acid anions and some H⁺. The cathodic reaction involves the reduction of cations, and the reactions that can be induced by reduction are as follows:

58V

Comparing the values of the standard electrode potential in ethanol medium, Cu²⁺ is first reduced because of the high standard electrode potential of copper. If H⁺ is to discharge in solution, the concentration of Cu²⁺ should be about 2.18×10⁻²⁰ mol·L⁻¹. However, the concentration of Cu²⁺ in the solution cannot be reduced due to the oxidation of copper at the anode. Finally, the reduction of Cu²⁺ takes place at the cathode. i.e. Cu²⁺ + 2e → Cu. Then, when the power is turned off, the electrolysis process is stopped and a transient reverse current is generated, leading to the battery process at the electrodes. Finally, some of the deposited copper is oxidized at the cathode, and at that moment some capric acid and copper caprate around the cathode are formed, which modify the hydrophobic groups of copper caprate on the coarse structure of the cathode copper plate.

Therefore, copper caprate with hydrophobic groups is produced on the cathode surface.

Effect of DC voltage on surface morphology and wettability of samples

Fig. 4 shows SEM images of the sample surface obtained under different voltages for 3 h. As shown in Fig. 4a, a papillary structure was formed at a voltage of 10 V. Fig 4b shows SEM images of the sample surface at a voltage of 20 V, where the nipple structure began to

agglomerate as a nipple particle randomly distributed on the surface, and hierarchical micro/nanostructures were formed. As shown in Fig. 4c and d, when the voltage is increased to 30 and 40 V, respectively, the lump-like papillary particles form larger papillary particles. In Fig. 4e and f, the voltages were 50 and 60 V, respectively, with the papillary structure assembled with the mushroom head structure and larger in size.

Fig. 4. SEM images of superhydrophobic surfaces obtained at different voltages; (a) 10 V, (b) 20 V, (c) 30 V, (d) 40 V, (e) 50 V, and (f) 60 V.

As shown in Fig. 4, the shape of the surface was changed with the DC voltage. The contact angle of the obtained surface at different voltages is measured and shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5 Variation of water contact angle with DC voltage.

As shown in Fig. 5, the largest contact angle was obtained at 10 V, 140.5° and at 20 V, 151.5°. As the voltage increased further, the contact angle decreased continuously. This indicates that an increase in the DC voltage causes the aggregation of the nipples and thus prevents the formation of

superhydrophobic structures of micro/nanostructures.

From the above results, the surface prepared at 20V voltage exhibits the best superhydrophobicity.

Effect of deposition time on surface morphology and wettability of samples

To investigate the effect of deposition time on wettability, SEM images of the prepared surfaces at 20 V and different deposition times are shown in Fig. 6.

As shown in Fig. 6, when the deposition time was 60, 90, 120, and 150 min (Fig. 6a-d), the small papillary particles began to connect with each other and at 180 min (Fig. 6e), they exhibited a superhydrophobic structure with a hierarchical micro/nanostructure structure. However, when the deposition time was 210 min (Fig. 6f), the papillary structure began to aggregate with each other, and the size of the particles became larger, leaving the superhydrophobic structure. It is shown that the deposition time at 20 V is 180 min, which exhibits excellent superhydrophobicity.

Fig. 6. SEM images of superhydrophobic films prepared at different times at a voltage of 20 V; (a) 60 min, (b) 90 min, (c) 120 min, (d) 150 min, (e) 180 min, and (f) 210 min

Fig. 7 shows the variation of water contact angle with different times at a voltage of 20 V.

Fig.7 Variation of water contact angle with time at a voltage of 20 V

As shown in Fig. 7, the highest water contact angle (151.5°) is obtained when the deposition time is 180 min at a voltage of 20 V.

Self-cleaning ability of the sample surface

The self-cleaning test of the sample surface was carried out using graphite powder. The copper plates and the prepared samples were sprayed with graphite powder and their self-cleaning ability was examined by immersing them in water and removing them. The

results are shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Comparison of self-cleaning tests of copper plates and fabricated superhydrophobic surfaces.

As shown in Fig. 8, the graphite powder remained intact on the copper plate after immersion and withdrawal, and the surface of the sample with superhydrophobic film was clear with the washing of graphite powder. It can be seen that the prepared

superhydrophobic surface has excellent self-cleaning ability.

Corrosion Resistance of the Sample Surface

The corrosion problem of metals is very wide and serious in actual production. Therefore, it is very important to improve the corrosion resistance of metals in real production. Here, superhydrophobic coating is one way to suppress corrosion. The corrosion resistance test was carried out on a classical three-electrode cell in 3.5% NaCl aqueous solution. A platinum electrode, prepared sample surface and saturated calomel electrode were used as the counter electrode, working electrode, and the reference electrode, respectively. The results are shown in Fig. 9.

As shown in Fig. 9, the potention-dynamic polarization (Tafel) curves of the original and prepared superhydrophobic copper plates show the corrosion resistance of the corresponding samples, respectively. The corrosion potential is larger than that of the original copper plate, and the corrosion current is lower in the opposite direction. Potention-dynamic polarization tests are shown in Table 1. As shown in Table 1, the corrosion potential of the original copper plate and superhydrophobic copper plate is -0.298V and -0.249 V, respectively, and the corrosion current is 5.16×10^{-5} A/cm² and 9.15×10^{-7} A/cm², respectively.

Fig. 9. Potention-dynamic polarization (Tafel) curves of copper plates and superhydrophobic copper plates in 3.5% NaCl solution.

Table 1. Corrosion potential and corrosion current of copper plates and superhydrophobic copper plates in 3.5% NaCl solution

Sample	$E_{corr}(V)$	$I_{corr}(A/cm^2)$
Copper plate	-0.298	5.16×10^{-5}
Superhydrophobic copper plate	-0.249	9.15×10^{-7}

The corrosion rate (V) of the samples can be calculated by the following Eq. (1): [13]

$$V = \frac{IKE}{dA} \quad (1)$$

where I represents corrosion density. A, d, and E are the area, the density and equivalent weight of the sample, respectively. K is a constant that defines the units for corrosion rate. The corrosion rate and corrosion current were positively correlated according to Eq. (1). The corrosion rate is lower for superhydrophobic copper plates than for copper plates.

This is because the superhydrophobic copper plate is filled with air in the micro/nano rough structure, reducing the actual contact area with the corrosion liquid.

The corrosion resistance of copper plates and superhydrophobic copper plates can be more accurately analyzed by Nyquist plots.

Fig. 10 Nyquist plot of copper plates and superhydrophobic copper plates in 3.5% NaCl solution.

As shown in Fig. 10, the Nyquist plot of the sample surface in 3.5% NaCl solution shows different curves due to the charge transfer resistance during corrosion. Compared with the original copper plate, the bends of the superhydrophobic copper plate have a wide distribution, because they form a protective surface film of copper caprate. This indicates that the charge transfer resistance of the initial copper plate and superhydrophobic copper plate increases gradually during the etching process.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we successfully prepared superhydrophobic copper film with micro/nanostructures with excellent corrosion resistance by electrochemical deposition and modification of capric acid groups. The superhydrophobic copper surface obtained by electrochemical deposition at 20 V for 3 h exhibits excellent corrosion resistance. Compared with the original copper plate, the corrosion current of the fabricated superhydrophobic copper surface is as low as 9.15×10^{-7} A/cm² and 1/50 of the original copper plate. This study shows that the superhydrophobic copper film with excellent corrosion resistance can be prepared by simple electrochemical deposition method.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kim Yong Nam: performed the preparation and characterization of the superhydrophobic copper surface. Ri Won Li, Kim Kyong Chol, Kim Jang Hak: assisted with the experiments and data analysis. Kim Yong Nam : wrote the manuscript. Kim Jong Guk: reviewed and edited the manuscript.

Declaration of Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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